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Prioritizing Critical Factors for Medical Supply Hub Location under Post-Pandemic Demand Uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic revealed significant weaknesses in global and regional medical supply chains, particularly in the timely and efficient distribution of critical medical supplies. In response to these challenges, the strategic selection of distribution hub locations has become increasingly vital to ensure rapid response and equitable access during future health crises. However, this decision-making process is inherently complex due to high levels of uncertainty in post-pandemic demand patterns and the subjective judgments of decision-makers. This study aims to address these challenges by incorporating expert opinions under uncertainty using the Bayesian Best-Worst Method (B-BWM). B-BWM allows for a robust integration of expert preferences and uncertainty, providing probabilistic weights for each criterion rather than deterministic scores. Through consultations with experts, the study evaluates factors such as accessibility, infrastructure resilience, proximity to population centers, and scalability. Results show that “Accessibility” was identified as the most important criterion (weight = 0.208), followed by “Infrastructure Reliability” (0.157) and “Disaster Risk” (0.150). Other criteria such as Demand Flexibility (0.092), Population Coverage (0.084), Regulatory (0.091), Cost Efficiency (0.084), Scalability (0.084), and Social Acceptance (0.050) received relatively lower weights. This study offers a systematic approach to decision-making under uncertainty, contributing to the development of more resilient and responsive healthcare supply networks. The results provide practical insights for policymakers and logistics planners in designing distribution infrastructures for critical medical supplies.

KEYWORDS – Medical Supply Hub, B-BWM, Multi-Criteria Decision-Making, Demand Uncertainty

1 INTRODUCTION

In the post-COVID-19 pandemic, critical gaps in the health supply chain have emerged in health systems around the world, along with critical challenges. It is therefore increasingly important to explore innovative and proactive approaches to healthcare that prioritize critical factors along the supply chain. Safeguarding lives and preserving social stability require the establishment of an efficient emergency medical supply distribution system and the prompt delivery of such goods after public health emergencies [1]. Managing the entire process has been complicated by the uncertainty

of demand in this environment. The demand for different medicines at various times in hospitals needs to be carefully assessed [2]. Additionally, because medications are perishable, inventory control and drug distribution management under such circumstances are essential to preventing human casualties and enhancing patient health [3].

Determining the requirements of the supply hub requires careful consideration of the criteria in order to deliver the most efficient supply of medical materials in the post-pandemic period. In terms of solution effectiveness, approaching the problem using Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) frameworks is crucial to take into account the complex nature of these criteria and their communication. A gap in the current knowledge is shown by the small number of studies that carefully analyse and categorize the criteria, according to the review of the literature. The Bayesian Best-Worst Method (B-BWM) was used in this study to examine and rank the requirements for choosing a medical supply hub. The B-BWM method has benefits for taking into consideration the level of hesitancy in expert evaluations and modelling intricate interactions between criteria [4]. By reducing the possibility of error while comparing pairs of criteria, B-BWM improves the reliability of the results [5]. This provides the decision-making process with a more precise and reliable framework. Accordingly, the main purpose of the study is to define the critical factors required for determining the medical supply hub location under demand uncertainty after the pandemic and to analyse their relationships with each other to provide a holistic perspective to decision makers. Addressing the existing gap in the literature, this study aims to more accurately define supply processes in the healthcare supply chain under uncertainty.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

When studies addressing the location selection of medical supply hubs have been investigated, the following papers have been encountered prominently. Sawant et al. [6] aim to plan a medical oxygen supply chain network in the face of unpredictable demand. Gómez-Pérez [7] propose to conduct survey research in accordance with WHO recommendations to assess the COVID-19 readiness of African healthcare facilities. Liu et al. [8] present a model using the MCDM approach for emergency medical supply distribution centers' site decisions in uncertain environments. Kritchanhai et al. [9] research the improvement of Thailand's COVID-19 Home Isolation kit home delivery distribution network. Zhou et al. [10] suggest to build a model of the ideal location for the urban emergency medical supplies distribution center based on NSGA-II. Li and Du [11] examine the research on the distribution of materials and the distribution of public health incidents during the previous 20 years starting in 2021. Yingzhen et al. [12] provide a dual-use medical center architecture concept that minimizes the number of medical centers and the separation between demand points and medical centers. When the studies are analyzed, it is seen that they have similar aims, but differences are noticeable in terms of the conditions considered and the methods adopted. While some studies do not take into account situations where uncertainty is at an extreme level, such as pandemics or post-pandemics, some studies do not use any method to reflect uncertainty. In this study, Bayesian B-BWM will be used for the first time to examine and rank the requirements for medical supply center selection. It can be claimed that this study will fill an important gap in the literature in terms of both the way the problem is addressed and the methods adopted.

3 BAYESIAN BEST WORST METHOD

The BWM, a recent MCDM technique, which relies on pairwise comparisons and has gained popularity in various decision-making contexts due to its simplicity and effectiveness [13], [14]. Compared to the widely-used Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), BWM significantly reduces the number of pairwise comparisons, thus offering time-efficiency advantages [15]. In BWM, decision-makers first identify the most important (best) and the least important (worst) criteria [16]. Subsequently, comparisons are only conducted between these two criteria and the remaining ones, simplifying the evaluation process considerably [17].

While methods such as fuzzy AHP and fuzzy DEMATEL have also been widely used for handling uncertainty and subjectivity in decision-making, they generally represent uncertainty using membership functions or grey numbers. Fuzzy AHP, for instance, extends AHP by incorporating fuzzy numbers into pairwise comparisons, thereby capturing vagueness in expert judgments [18]. Fuzzy DEMATEL is effective for modelling causal relationships among criteria under uncertainty [19]. However, both methods often require a larger number of pairwise comparisons, increasing cognitive burden on experts, and their aggregation rules may not fully account for the probabilistic diversity of multiple expert opinion.

However, a critical limitation of traditional BWM is its reliance solely on individual decision-maker judgments. Although group decision-making approaches have been proposed to overcome this limitation [20], they typically do not incorporate probabilistic elements into the aggregation of multiple expert opinions. In contrast, the B-BWM offers unique methodological advantages: it explicitly models the uncertainty and variability among experts' preferences in a probabilistic framework, enabling the direct calculation of confidence intervals or probability distributions for each criterion's weight. This probabilistic aggregation reduces information loss and offers more robust results, particularly in complex or high-uncertainty contexts. To address this gap and minimize information loss, Mohammadi and Rezaei developed the B-BWM [21], which aggregates multiple expert opinions from a probabilistic perspective. The B-BWM has been successfully implemented across various domains and applications [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29].

This study adopts the B-BWM approach for prioritizing critical factors in the selection of medical supply distribution hubs under post-pandemic demand uncertainty. The B-BWM steps can be summarized as follows:

Step 1. Define a set of criteria $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\}$.

Step 2. Each expert identifies the most important (best) and least important (worst) criteria from set C , denoted respectively as C_B^k and C_W^k , for each expert k . At this stage, no pairwise comparisons are needed.

Step 3. Experts perform pairwise comparisons between the best criterion and all other criteria using a scale from 1 (equal importance) to 9 (extremely more important). This generates the Best-to-Others vector for each expert k .

$$A_B^k = (a_{B1}^k, a_{B2}^k, \dots, a_{Bn}^k), k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (1)$$

Step 4. Similarly, the worst criterion is compared pairwise with all remaining criteria, resulting in the Others-to-Worst vector for each expert

$$A_W^k = (a_{1W}^k, a_{2W}^k, \dots, a_{nW}^k)^T, k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (2)$$

Step 5. The vectors are then processed probabilistically using computational tools developed by Mohammadi and Rezaei [21]. Unlike classical BWM, B-BWM evaluates criterion weights as probability distributions, aggregated across multiple experts through a multinomial-Dirichlet Bayesian framework

$$(A_B^k | w^k) \sim \text{multinomial} \left(\frac{1}{w} \right), k = 1, \dots, K \quad (3)$$

$$(A_W^k | w^k) \sim \text{multinomial} (w^k), k = 1, \dots, K \quad (4)$$

$$(w^k | w^*) \sim \text{Dir}(\gamma x w^*), k = 1, \dots, K \quad (5)$$

$$\gamma \sim \text{gamma}(0.1, 0.1) \quad (6)$$

$$w^* \sim \text{Dir} (1) \quad (7)$$

Here $w^* = (w_1^*, w_2^*, \dots, w_n^*)$ is the aggregated weights vector, and the distributions are sampled and solved using Monte-Carlo simulation tools like JAGS, commonly employed in Bayesian analyses [21].

Generally, higher weights imply greater criterion importance in MCDM. However, when weight values are close, particularly in group decision-making, subtle differences must be carefully interpreted. At this stage, a credibility ranking demonstrates the robustness of a criterion's superiority over others, and it becomes especially critical.

4 APPLICATION

Firstly, the criteria for selecting medical supply distribution hub locations were identified through an extensive literature review and validated by expert opinions. These criteria, which comprehensively reflect operational, logistical, risk-related, and social considerations, are presented in Figure 1.

Site Selection Criteria for Medical Supply Distribution Hubs

Figure 1. Criteria set of problem

To determine the relative importance of criteria for medical supply distribution hub locations, the B-BWM was employed. Initially, decision-makers identified the most critical (best) and the least critical (worst) criteria based on their expert judgments, as illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4. The most and the least important main criteria by experts

	Best	Worst
E-1	Accessibility	Social Acceptance
E-2	Accessibility	Social Acceptance
E-3	Accessibility	Social Acceptance

Based on the evaluations summarized in Table 4, all three experts identified "Accessibility" as the most important criterion for selecting a medical supply distribution hub location, highlighting the critical role of efficient transport and ease of access. Conversely, "Social Acceptance" was consistently selected as the least important criterion by all experts, indicating that operational and logistical considerations take precedence over community approval in this context.

As presented in Table 4, the experts' "Best-to-Others" and "Others-to-Worst" comparison vectors formed the basis for calculating the optimal weights of each criterion for every decision-maker.

Table 5. Decision vectors for the main criteria

	Best-to-Others	Others-to-Worst
E-1	1,2,3,4,4,2,2,5,4	7,5,5,2,5,6,6,1,2
E-2	1,3,6,5,4,2,7,9,4	9,8,3,2,4,7,4,1,3
E-3	1,2,4,3,5,3,6,7,4	7,6,4,5,3,5,2,1,4

MATLAB r2021b was utilized to compute the optimal weights for each site selection criterion. The MATLAB codes developed by Mohammadi and Rezaei [30] were adapted to implement the B-BWM approach from a probabilistic perspective. As a result, the calculated weights for the criteria are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Weights of the criteria

According to the weights illustrated in Figure 2, “Accessibility” emerges as the most critical criterion for the selection of medical supply distribution hub locations, underscoring the importance of efficient and reliable access routes. “Infrastructure Reliability” and “Disaster Risk” are also highly prioritized, highlighting the need for resilient facilities in safe areas. In most MCDM approaches, criteria with higher weights are considered more influential; however, in some cases, weight differences are marginal, which can complicate the ranking process, particularly in group decision-making scenarios. In such instances, credal ranking becomes valuable, as it clarifies the degree of dominance between criteria. The credal ranking results for this study are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Credal ranking graph of criteria

The credal ranking graph presented in Fig. 3 displays the confidence levels regarding the relative importance of each pair of site selection criteria for medical supply distribution hubs. The numeric labels on the arrows denote the confidence with which experts assert that criterion X is more significant than criterion Y (i.e., $X \xrightarrow{r} Y$). Higher values indicate greater confidence in the dominance of one criterion over another.

According to Fig. 7, Accessibility (C1) stands out as the most influential criterion, with high confidence levels against nearly all other criteria, highlighting its perceived dominance in ensuring efficient and reliable distribution operations. This consensus emphasizes the necessity of strategic placement with optimal access to transportation networks. Infrastructure Reliability (C2) also exhibits strong dominance, particularly over Scalability (C9) and Social Acceptance (C8), reflecting expert consensus on the importance of robust, dependable facilities for post-pandemic supply chain resilience. On the other hand, Social Acceptance (C8) consistently receives lower confidence values when compared to operational or risk-based criteria, reinforcing the earlier result that community approval, while valuable, is not prioritized over logistical effectiveness and safety in emergency contexts. The credal ranking analysis corroborates the centrality of Accessibility, Infrastructure Reliability, and Disaster Risk in determining optimal hub locations, while also highlighting areas where expert confidence diverges. This perspective is significant for planners and policymakers aiming for robust and resilient medical supply chains under uncertainty.

5 DISCUSSION

In this study, the multi-criteria decision-making approach is adopted to analyse which factors should be prioritized for the selection of the medical supply hub location, considering the post-pandemic demand uncertainty. We used Bayesian networks to handle uncertainty, using probabilistic weights for each criterion instead of deterministic scores. According to the B-BWM results, the criterion with the highest weight was found to be "Accessibility". The accessibility factor for location selection problems has garnered more attention in recent years. It is also essential to have accessible access routes when selecting medical supply hub locations. "Accessibility", which is the most frequently used factor to evaluate the spatial equality of many facility location alternatives, is expressed as the ease of access for users/customers from one point to another [31]. Considering spatial accessibility is also important for identifying areas where medical services are inadequate under the uncertainty of changing demand after the pandemic, and developing strategies as a precaution [32]. Spatial accessibility is an important part of the health policy framework [33]. With the accessibility of medical facilities, equity of medical infrastructure is promoted, and the level of public health service is improved [31]. In addition to having a direct correlation with locals' health, the accessibility of healthcare services is a crucial metric for gauging social welfare and equity in an area [34].

"Infrastructure Reliability" emerges as the second most important factor for the health supply hub location selection problem addressed within the scope of this study. Numerous studies have addressed the issue of determining hub sites and routes during and after extreme periods in order to guarantee both economic advantage and network reliability [35]. Determining a reliable medical supply hub location helps prevent costly failures in extreme situations such as pandemics, accidents, outages, etc., contributes to public safety, and supports economic stability. It also helps prevent disaster risk, which is considered the third most important criterion. Based on all these supporting studies, it can be claimed that the results found in this study are reasonable and verifiable.

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, calculations were performed with the B-BWM methodology to identify and prioritize critical factors in order to position the medical supply center in the post-pandemic demand uncertainty environment. Bayesian networks were used to calculate the probabilistic weights of the identified critical factors instead of their exact scores, based on the opinions of three experts. The results showed that Accessibility (C1) is the most critical factor when locating a medical supply center. These results actually emphasize the importance of easily accessible, reliable facilities in

supply chains. In addition, Infrastructure Reliability (C2) was also revealed as the second most critical factor. These findings emphasize that the most important requirements for the provision of medical supplies are the need for an accessible supply chain and the necessary infrastructure security to ensure this. On the contrary, Social Acceptance (C8) was the least important criterion, again in agreement with the decision makers. While public support and approval is important for the proper management of the processes, it was rated as the least important compared to the efficient and successful realization of logistics processes in emergency situations. This study offers important implications for industry stakeholders, researchers and policy makers in the healthcare supply chain in general. It emphasizes the adoption of requirements and areas of focus that will enable the fastest and most accurate supply of medical supplies in the uncertain supply chain environment following the pandemic. In future studies, the framework can be extended by adding new criteria and different regions and conducting comparative analyses with more decision makers. In addition, the results of this study can be extended in future studies by applying different fuzzy-based MCDM methods. Thus, causal relationships can be verified by analysing the results with exact scores instead of probabilistic weights.

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